

Vascularized patient-derived tumoroids supplemented with immune cells to predict response towards treatment for lung cancer patients

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Abstract

We here describe a prototype of a patient-derived tumoroid that prefigures the precision medicine approach by helping experimental assessment of response to current treatments. The introduction of microvessels to help forming a tumor-connected vasculature, and of peripheral blood immune cells was shown to be essential for the representativeness of the model. The study is based on a cohort of 11 patients at various stages of the disease. Noteworthy, this predictive vascularized, and immunocompetent micromodel can be obtained within 2 weeks, matching the constraints of the patient journey. Histological analyses confirmed that major features of the original tumor were conserved. Transcriptomic analysis confirmed the functionality of the tumoroid. The responses to either anti-angiogenic treatment or platinum-based chemotherapy regimen highlighted the role of immune mechanisms. We also discussed the possibility to apply this original experimental model to the analysis of response to immune checkpoint blockers, or oncolytic vector-based therapies.

Introduction

Lung cancer represents 18% of all cancer deaths¹. Lung cancer is divided in two subsets: non-small-cell lung cancer (NSCLC) that affect 85% of lung cancer patients and small-cell lung cancer (SCLC) that affect the remaining 15%. 40% of NSCLC patients present an adenocarcinoma^{2 3}. Nearly half of the NSCLC patients are diagnosed at late stages⁴. As a consequence, the 5-year relative survival rate decreases to 6% despite the scope of treatments (chemotherapy, targeted therapy, and immunotherapy)⁵.

Currently, the treatment selection is based on three important methods: (i) NSCLC diagnosis stage, (ii) histological subtype, and (iii) molecular profile. The percentage of adenocarcinoma patients who are likely to present a genetic alteration such as KRAS or EGFR mutations can reach 60% of them^{6 7}. The identification of oncogenic drivers has led to the development of targeted therapies such as tyrosine kinase inhibitors of different mutations (e.g., EGFR, MET, ALK, ROS-1 ...). Targeted therapies have helped to improve objective responses rate and progression-free survival compared to chemotherapy. However, some patients can develop acquired resistance, leading to disease progression^{8 9}.

As an adjunct of chemotherapy and targeted therapy, immune checkpoint inhibitors (ICIs) have helped to improve patients' survival. This latter treatment aims to target immune checkpoint pathways to further promote antitumor immune response by increasing T cell responses. Despite the emergence of ICIs and their successful results during clinical trials, less than 30% of NSCLC patients at advanced stage are responders to pembrolizumab as 1st line treatment¹⁰.

Regarding these clinical issues, inter-patients' heterogeneity is highly taken into consideration. This impels us to develop new and improved preclinical models for better prediction of treatments efficiency.

Nowadays, the trend relates to patients' derived tumoroids (PDTs). They have been explored and have led to numerous models. Indeed, they have proven to recapitulate the main features of the lung primary tissue. Following the several alternatives of PDTs models, a key issue was raised: are they applicable and reliable to complete drug screening studies besides current preclinical oncology models?

Among current lung tumoroids models, the tumor-extrinsic factors such as stromal and immune cells have been missing. Moreover, the generation of PDTs mainly involve murine-based growth factors including Matrigel[®]^{11,12,13,14,15}. And in this way, our objective is to represent the tumor complexity by incorporating cells that are mainly involved in tumoral progression and tumoral therapeutic responses.

For that purpose, we will form PDTs in a scaffold-free condition as described by Seitlinger et al.¹⁶. Indeed, the addition of exogenous cells such as human pulmonary fibroblasts is necessary¹⁶. To gain insights in terms of precision medicine, we worked on the optimization of this model to further propose an autologous model. The engineering consists in the use of adipose tissue derived microvessels (ad-MVs)¹⁷. Ad-MVs provide a natural source of vascularization into the model. As they

are derived from the adipose tissue, they contain intact microvascular fragments, more precisely, intact arteriolar, capillary and venules vessel segments to facilitate the generation of a microvasculature¹⁸. Ad-MVs provide a high vascularization potential for tissue engineering and modeling¹⁹. Hannah et al. demonstrated the feasibility and robustness of forming vascularized organoids with ad-MVs and mesenchymal stem cells for studying metabolic diseases including diabetes and obesity¹⁷.

In our model, this integrated microvasculature can help the formation dynamics of Vasc-PDTs by mimicking physiological process of angiogenesis in vitro. Indeed, tumor cells are known to remodel the vasculature through the process of tumor angiogenesis²⁰. Thus, ad-MVs as supportive cells in the PDT model, will constitute a relevant model of tumor progression like angiogenesis.

The use of ad-MVs as supportive cells didn't interfere with specific patients' tumoral signature. We can find patients' tumorigenicity and specificity in our PDT model by immunofluorescence and transcriptomic characterization.

Besides mimicking angiogenesis in vitro, we aim to maintain each patient's unique immune signature. As mentioned in our previous review, some limitations have been reported in the described lung cancer organoids (e.g., lack of cell types from the tumor microenvironment (TME)). To better optimize this, the use of autologous peripheral blood immune cells (PBMCs) will permit to maintain the TME complexity in vitro²¹. Co-culture of PDTs with PBMCs permit to address several points: (i) infiltration and trafficking in PDTs, and (ii) cytotoxicity activity of autologous immune cells.

Here, we propose an innovative PDT model which meets the requirements of TME reconstitution for standard of care assessment and a relevant predictivity according to clinical patients' specificity in a short time prior therapeutic decision. We also discuss the possibility to apply this original experimental model to the analysis of response to immune checkpoint blockers, or oncolytic vector-based therapies.

Results And Discussion

Vascularized patient-derived tumoroids (Vasc-PDTs) display major markers of original tumors

The functional mimicry, and by extension the clinical relevance, of Vasc-PDTs was characterized by immunohistochemistry, and by 3'-RNA sequencing.

Histological analysis confirmed that all patients enrolled in this study were adenocarcinomas (including one large cell carcinoma) (**Table 1**). In a subset of 4 patients for which original tumor cell features were compared to their respective patient-derived tumoroids (PDTs), we could observe the similarity of TTF-1, Ki-67, cytokeratin-7, mucin-1 profile features between patient-derived tumoroids (PDTs) and their original tumor counterparts (**Fig. 1**). For memory, TTF-1 is a marker for epithelial-mesenchymal transition, used concomitantly with Ki-67, a marker of cell proliferation²², and with cytokeratin-7, and mucin-1, as predictive markers of tumor growth and metastasis^{23,24}. All samples were negative for p40, the sensitive and specific marker for distinguishing lung squamous cell carcinoma from adenocarcinoma.

Heterologous ad-MVs were added to the PDTs to form Vasc-PDTs both to generate a microvasculature, and as supportive cells in the tumoroid culture process. We first characterized the microvasculature into our model of Vasc-PDTs. At day seven of the culture, tumoroids are well-formed and first, we characterized the ad-MVs within PDTs (**Supplementary Fig. 1**). To characterize the presence of lumen in endothelial cells and structures, we used Ulex Europaeus Agglutinin I-lectin (UEA I-lectin) which is an excellent marker of human endothelial cells. It binds to glycoproteins and glycolipids placed on the extracellular side of the vascular membrane^{25,26}. The preservation of the MV lumen is observed with the UEA-lectin staining (**Supplementary Fig. 1**). Ad-MVs kept their structure and functionality into PDTs, but lack of a hierarchical microvasculature. We have also performed IHC staining of endothelial cells with the CD31 marker either on primary tissue or Vasc-PDT. We

could show that CD31 was present in both types of samples. Comparative IHC of primary tissue and Vasc-PDTs showed maintenance of primary tumor cells markers.

To further characterize our 3D model, we performed the 3'RNA sequencing on four patients to compare their gene expression profiles to the tumoral primary cells. Indeed, we wanted to study if the addition of exogenous cells, the ad-MVs, could modify the transcriptomic of Vasc-PDTs. For that, 3' RNA sequencing is based on a differential analysis of two conditions. In our case, it is the comparison of either tumor primary cells versus healthy primary cells or vascularized tumoroids versus healthy organoids. Among the four patients that were characterized by IHC, we focused on the 3 patients: patient 21T 414, patient 21T 469 and patient 21T 554 where significant differences were observed between the tumoral samples and the healthy samples.

Our vasc-PDT model displayed a characteristic gene transcriptomic signatures of lung adenocarcinoma, including EPCAM, CK7 (or KRT7), MUC1 and TTF-1. The similitude of upregulated genes between the tumoral primary cells and the Vasc-PDT is represented in the Volcano Plot graph. We could observe that lung adenocarcinoma associated genes were also upregulated in the Vasc-PDTs versus the matched healthy organoids. (Fig. 2A). The main lung adenocarcinoma genes observed in the Vasc-PDT model were summarized (Fig. 2B). Among TTF-1, EPCAM, CK7 (or KRT7) and MUC1, more genes of the cytokeratin's family were found either in the tumoral primary cells or in the PDTs (KRT6A, KRT8, KRT18 and KRTCAP3)²⁷. Genes such as NAPS1 and S100P were observed in our Vasc-PDT in accordance with the tumoral primary cells. They were previously observed in lung adenocarcinoma and are implicated in tumor development and metastasis²⁸. Otherwise, genes of the SERPIN family and particularly SERPINA1 gene, are involved in the pathogenesis of lung cancer²⁹. Other common genes were also maintained in culture such as CEACAM5 and CEACAM6 in patients 21T 414 and 21T 554. CEACAM5 is overexpressed in 20% of NSCLC patients and is even the subject of a therapeutic target : tusamitamab ravtansine (SAR408701) which is an antibody-drug conjugate currently in phase 3^{30 31}. In the Vasc-PDTs, some other upregulated genes are found compared to the tumoral primary cells. For example, in the tumoroids derived: from patient 21T554, we could find upregulated expression of KRT15, S100A8, SERPINE1 and SLC34A2 (among other genes) and not on the tumoral primary cells. Ex vivo growth, culture conditions and time of culture can influence the formation of patient-derived tumoroids³². Comparative 3'-RNA sequencing of primary tumory cells, and Vasc-PDTs showed maintenance of primary tumor cells features within Vasc-PDTs. Overall, the tumoroids could retain the histological and transcriptomic characteristics of the primary cells.

Our Vasc-PDT model showed the ability to preserve the typical structure of ad-MVs. Following the characterization part, drug sensitivity is verified by assessing the antiangiogenic treatment using the common angiogenesis in vitro assay.

Assessment of anti-angiogenic drug in Vasc-PDTs: Ad-MVs provided a suitable microvasculature to assess sensitivity to anti-angiogenic treatments

At day seven, tumoroids were transferred into an insert containing a hydrogel matrix³³ based on a fibrin gel as illustrated (Fig. 3A). This matrix embedded Vasc-PDTs to favor the formation of typical capillary-like structures called "sproutings". This protocol can provide a tool to study angiogenesis in vitro. One day after embedding, we confirmed with CD31 staining that these capillary-like structures were endothelial cells and not only with observational statements such as brightfield imaging or phalloidin staining for example^{34,35}(Fig. 3B).

A clinical concentration of 250µg.ml⁻¹ of an approved antiangiogenic drug for lung cancer (bevacizumab, assessed during 96h) was used to validate our in vitro angiogenesis model³⁶. Bevacizumab is an antiangiogenic monoclonal antibody that is directed against VEGF-A. VEGF-A plays a central role in blood vessel development and binds to one of its receptors, VEGFR-2, to promote vasculogenesis and angiogenesis³⁷. It is an approved therapy for unresectable, locally advanced, or recurrent non-squamous NSCLC. The progression-free survival in clinical has been reported to be in average 4.4 months³⁸. To assess the bevacizumab effect on vascularized PDTs, antiangiogenic effect is confirmed according to four clinical

criteria : (i) inhibition of new vessel growth, (ii) regression of newly formed tumor vasculature, (iii) alteration of vascular function and (iv) direct effects on tumor cells³⁹. After 96h of treatment, we noticed a decrease of the cell viability in tumoroids treated with bevacizumab as compared to untreated PDTs. The inhibition and regression of newly capillary-like structures are confirmed with IHC staining of CD31 (Fig. 3B). Low density of endothelial cells in Vasc-PDTs treated with anti-VEGF is observed. To provide more precision on the antiangiogenic effect, different levels of soluble proteins implied in angiogenesis were studied (see Materials and methods). We have observed a significant decrease of VEGF-A, a soluble protein which is implied in proliferation and migration of endothelial cells, vascular permeability and the selection of tip and stalk cells. Thus, by blocking VEGF-A, there's an inhibition of the growth and metastasis processes of tumors (Fig. 3D)⁴⁰. Thus, we could demonstrate the functionality of these pseudo-microvascular network under an antiangiogenic treatment.

Also, we can observe an increase of IL-8 and EGF for the patients tested. IL-8 is a known proinflammatory cytokine implied in angiogenesis and tumor growth. Other studies have demonstrated a link between these two proteins⁴¹. Zhang et al. demonstrate that EGF could directly lead to IL-8 production, inducing cancer cells proliferation⁴². This result suggests that anti-VEGF treatment acts as expected on the neo-capillary like structures but not specifically on tumoral cells. Based on that, bevacizumab was approved by the medical authorities in first line and maintenance of advanced non-squamous NSCLC treatment combined to platinum-based treatment⁴³.

An effect on tumor cells is observable since the cell viability of tumoroids treated with anti-VEGF decreased by 50% on average (Fig. 3C). Taken together, we successfully established a protocol to generate a pseudo-vascularized network into Vasc-PDT for diverse applications: (i) decipher tumor-endothelial cells' interactions, (ii) study angiogenesis mechanism and (iii) study a potential antiangiogenic effect of a drug.

The absence of UEA I-lectin staining reflected the absence of lumen in these developed structures. Next step would be to have a lumenization in these "sproutings". This can be improved with the addition of pro-angiogenic growth factors such as FGF-2 that inhibits endothelial cell apoptosis and HGF that promotes endothelial cell growth and motility from the beginning of the Vasc-PDTs culture⁴⁴.

Co-culture of Vasc-PDTs with autologous PBMCs permits to reconstitute a dynamic infiltrate of immune cells

After having checked the contribution of ad-MVs into the generation of Vasc-PDT, the presence of an immune tumor microenvironment was then checked. In the lung tumor microenvironment, different immune cells populations are known to actively participate for promotion or regression of lung cancer⁴⁵. Among them, T lymphocytes infiltrating tumors, especially the CD4 + and CD8 + T cells promote cytotoxic functions in the tumoral microenvironment. B cells infiltrating tumors are also positively involved in the tumoral microenvironment. Their presence correlates with a better prognosis. For that, the presence of CD45 + cells in dissociated primary tissues and Vasc-PDTs were priorly verified. The analysis for immune cells populations present in the primary tissue versus tumoroids was performed by using flow cytometry. The gating strategy is illustrated in supplementary data (Fig. 4). As observed in our previous experiments, a decrease of immune cells was observed along the culture (data not shown).

Thereby we present our strategy of immune cells enhancement by using autologous immune cells derived from peripheral blood. Co-culture of Vasc-PDTs with autologous PBMCs, for at least 72h, was done to permit the infiltration. The subpopulations from each patient were priorly studied by flow cytometry to check the viability and proportions of the different immune cells' population (**Supplementary Fig. 5**). Variability can be noted in the PBMC subpopulations depending on the patient. For example, patients 22T 194, 22T 245 and 21269-008 presented more lymphocytes populations quantitatively than others. To determine if the PBMCs had infiltrated the Vasc-PDT, flow cytometry acquisitions had been performed to determine the proportions of CD45 + immune cells within the infiltrated Vasc-PDTs. We could show an increase of immune cells populations when co-culture with autologous PBMCs was performed (Fig. 4A and 4B). The increase was more significant than Vasc-PDTs without co-culture for the three patients previously cited.

After having assessed the proportions of immune cells, the localization of CD8 + T cells was checked by IHC. We observed an augmentation of immune cells proportions in the Vasc-PDTs that were priorly co-cultured with autologous PBMCs. What is interesting is that we even found presence of CD8 + cells when co-culture was performed in one patient. According to these results, Vasc-PDTs enrichment with autologous PBMCs is feasible to reconstitute a dynamic infiltrate of immune cells.

Assessment of chemotherapy in a reconstituted tumor microenvironment

Tumoroids killing was checked with the cell viability assay (based on metabolic activity) on Vasc-PDTs alone and Vasc-PDTs in co-culture to study a potential cytotoxic activity of autologous PBMCs. Cell viability of tumoroids decrease significantly under chemotherapy regimen (cisplatin plus pemetrexed) in both conditions. LPS was used as a control to preserve PBMCs activity and no decrease of viability was observed (Fig. 4c). Chemotherapy regimen could significantly decrease the viability of Vasc-PDTs with or without PBMCs co-culture, however, no significative effect was observed. This could be explained by the lack of cytotoxic activity mediated by CD8 + T cells. Indeed, concentrations of IFN- γ released were assessed in the supernatants. Levels of IFN- γ were higher in the LPS conditions (**Supplementary Fig. 6A**). This showed a lack of tumor cells destruction through the production of IFN- γ led by CD8 + T cells.

After assessing the potential cytotoxicity of autologous PBMCs, the addition of autologous immune cells permitted to study some other features of therapeutics, that is to know: infiltration and activation of immune cells that lead to an antitumor response.

Standard of care chemotherapy has an impact on immune cells infiltration and activation profiles

Besides evaluating cells killing by chemotherapy regimen, we concentrated on the tumor microenvironment that may also affect drug response.

For that, the PBMCs infiltration toward Vasc-PDTs was compared among the three conditions tested (the untreated condition, the LPS and the treatment with chemotherapy) using flow cytometry. We didn't observe any increase of immune cells infiltration under chemotherapy. We could even observe a significant decrease of CD8+ T cells compared to the untreated condition. LPS condition didn't affect the viability and immune cells infiltration compared to chemotherapy. In this co-culture model, chemotherapy treatment could present a direct killing of PBMCs resulting in a decrease of trafficking and infiltration (Fig. 4D).

Then, 14 different proteins implied in immune-checkpoint regulations and in T cells activation were analyzed. Proteins were priorly isolated from Vasc-PDTs in all conditions.

Significatively, chemotherapy regimen decreased the level of these proteins. Among these immunosuppressive proteins, we can focus on BTLA which was significantly decreased. BTLA is a recently discovered immunosuppressive receptor of the CD28 superfamily with CTLA-4 and PD-L1/PD-1. The BTLA interacts with its ligand HVEM that lead to downregulation of the immune response by suppressing lymphocyte proliferation⁴⁶. This data showed that chemotherapy regimen could reverse the immunosuppressive tumor microenvironment. The levels of immunosuppressive proteins (CTLA-4, IDO, PD1, PD-L1) were also analyzed, but no significative effect was observed (**Fig. 4E, Supplementary Fig. 6B**).

Then, we focused on four costimulatory molecules involved in T cells activation (CD27, CD28, CD80 and CD137). The levels of CD27, CD28 and CD80 were significantly decreased by chemotherapy regimen.

Similarly, Zhou et al. explored the potential antitumor immune response under platinum-based chemotherapy in a co-culture model of A549 cells, neutrophils, and total immune cells. They demonstrated that platinum-based chemotherapy could induce an intracellular iron-dependent cell death called ferroptosis. This form of tumor cell death provokes an immune antitumoral response led by neutrophils that further leads to the enhancement of T cells infiltration and TH1

differentiation⁴⁷. Moreover, in xenograft murine models, it has been observed that cisplatin could lead to an upregulation of PD-L1 expression. This finding led to the potential of combining cisplatin to anti-PD-L1 in order to increase antitumor immune response⁴⁸.

With our proposed immuno-oncology PDT model, we can maintain some immune cells in culture and study the dynamic infiltrate toward Vasc-PDTs. Along the chemotherapy treatment, autologous PBMCs viability tend to decrease. PBMCs are anergized cells and maybe need to be activated. Cattaneo et al. described a protocol for generating tumor-reactive T cells from PBMCs³¹.

In order to study drugs' immunostimulatory effect, another strategy would be to apply the drug prior to adding autologous PBMCs. This can be achieved by treating tumoroids with chemo-attractive proteins such as CXCL chemokines to facilitate immune cells infiltration. Despite the absence of an integrated TME, here we demonstrate the feasibility of forming a Vasc-PDT that gathers autologous immune cells from the patient¹⁴.

Conclusion

PDTs are now evolving and constitute an innovative model in oncology as they can reproduce, in vitro, each patients' specific features. Our Vasc-PDT model proves its ability to maintain in culture the histological markers of the primary tissue. 3' RNA sequencing shows that Vasc-PDTs reproduce as faithfully as possible patients' tissues features by presenting the same upregulated genes as in the tumor primary tissue. Following this deep characterization, we test two clinical drugs indicated in lung cancer such as targeted therapy (antiangiogenic) and chemotherapy. Different profiles of sensitivity to both treatments are observable within only two weeks of culture. A short time response allows to save time for clinician therapeutic decision.

In summary, since the known implication of the TME in tumoral progression and metastasis, the presence of immunocompetent cells reveals to be useful for immunomodulatory treatments. The fact that we can maintain some patients' immune cells (tumor-infiltrating lymphocytes) and enrich our Vasc-PDT model with autologous immune cells, different readouts apart drug assessment can be performed. Besides immune checkpoint inhibitors, oncolytic virotherapy is an emergent and promising therapy based on the replication ability of viruses to lyse cancer cells and specific activation of the host immune response. A model associating the field of immunology to oncology permits to have many therapeutic applications including the assessment of immune-checkpoint inhibitors response (new therapies or drugs combination) and the assessment of a potential activation of immune cells response for virotherapy based-treatments for example.

Currently our Vasc-PDTs contain a heterologous source of ad-MVs. The final objective of this study is to develop an autologous model of vascularized PDTs for personalized medicine. This would be based on the concomitant removal of lung tissues, peripheral blood, and adipose tissue.

Materials And Methods

Human specimens. Biopsies of lung cancer were obtained by surgical resections at Hôpitaux Universitaires de Strasbourg, France, (7 patients) confirmed for their tumoral status by anatomopathological analysis. Patients' informed consents were managed by the *Centre de Ressources Biologiques*. Adenocarcinoma tissue samples paired with autologous whole blood were sourced from CRB, Strasbourg and Fidelis Research, Bulgaria. Ad-MVs were provided by Advanced Solutions, Manchester NH, USA. Ad-MVs were isolated from human subcutaneous adipose tissue and stored in liquid nitrogen until use.

Tissue preparation and culture of Vasc-PDTs with ad-MVs. After reception, human samples were washed in PBS to remove blood excess, then enzymatically digested at 37°C for 1h, with intermittent agitation. The media was then transferred to a Falcon tube through 70µM cell strainers. Strained cells were centrifuged, and pellets were resuspended in 1mL of lysis

buffer to remove remaining blood cells. A second centrifugation was performed, and left cells were resuspended in 1 mL DMEM-F12 (ref. BE12-719F, Lonza). Other cells entering the composition of PDTs were prepared in parallel. For the formation of tumoroids and organoids with ad-MVs, after the tissue preparation described previously, cells from Advanced Solutions® were thawed in the water bath then centrifuged at 400g during 4min. The ad-MVs pellet is then resuspended in RPMI media supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS), 1% gentamycin, B-27 (ref. 17504044, ThermoFisher Scientific) and human-recombinant VEGF (ref. PHC9394, ThermoFisher Scientific). Ad-MVs and patients' dissociated cells were mixed according to a ratio of 1:50. The mixed cells suspension were then seeded for a final volume of 200µL in ULA plates. Vasc-PDTs are usually formed after 7 days of incubation at 37°C.

3' RNA sequencing. Pipeline for raw data processing. Raw paired reads generated by high-throughput sequencing were first processed using a bioinformatic pipeline developed with the tool Snakemake⁴⁹. Briefly, 3 extra G added during library preparation were removed from read 2 using trimmomatic⁵⁰. Then, the Unique Molecular Identifier (UMI) sequence was extracted from read 1 and appended to the name of the paired read 2 (extract function from the UMI-tools package⁵¹. Read 2 from each pair were then mapped against the reference genome (GRCh37) with STAR⁵². Reads mapped at a given position of the genome with identical or near identical UMI sequence were deduplicated with the program umi_tools dedup, using the method "directional". Readcount per cellular and viral gene was then determined with the program htseq-count, mode "union"⁵³.

Read count normalization and differential gene expression analysis. To account for potential differences in sequencing depth between samples, read count was normalized with DESeq2⁵⁴. A gene was considered differentially expressed comparing two conditions if the adjusted p value (Benjamini and Hochberg method) was ≤ 0.1 and the absolute fold change ≥ 2 .

GO enrichment analyses. Lists of genes differentially expressed (either up or down-regulated) between 2 experimental conditions were used as input for GO enrichment analyses with the function enrichGO from the R package cluster Profiler⁵⁵. Comparative analyses were also performed with the function compareCluster from the same package.

Peripheral Blood Mononuclear cells (PBMCs) isolation. Autologous blood sample was delivered with tumoral tissue by CRB and Fidelis Research. Firstly, blood was diluted with an equal volume of PBS and mixed slowly. A falcon with Ficoll Paque Plus reagent (ref. 17144003, Cytiva) was prepared and diluted blood was carefully overlaid to begin density gradient separation. Centrifugation was performed with the brake off. PBMC layer was carefully collected in another falcon. Once the density gradient separation was done, three washing steps were performed to remove the contaminants as described in the following step. PBS was added to the collected PBMCs, and centrifugation was performed. After PBS washings steps, lysis buffer was added to remove the remaining blood cells. Then, centrifugation was performed, and the cells were resuspended in PBS. After PBMC isolation, PBMC are cryopreserved in 10% DMSO 20% FBS diluted in RPMI media and stored at -80°C before co-culturing autologous PBMC with Vasc-PDTs at day 7 of the culture time and the infiltration is left for at least 72h.

Angiogenesis in vitro assay. At day 7 of the culture, inserts were prepared the day of the PDTs transfer. Fibrin gel is pipetted into cell culture inserts (Thincert 665 610 Greiner Bio-One) that are placed in the 12 wells plate. Preparation of fibrin gel is described in a previous article. The inserts are then transferred in the incubator for at least 30min, then, 600µL of RPMI media supplemented with VEGF, FGF-2, EGF, HGF and B27 were added in the 12 wells plate. After 30min of incubation at 37°C, the formed tumoroids were laid on the fibrin gel for at least 24h to observe the formation of endothelial cells structures.

Co-culture of Vasc-PDTs and PBMCs. At day 7 of the culture, PBMCs were thawed and counted to start with the co-culture. To stimulate T cells proliferation, IL-2 was added in the RPMI media at final concentrations of 20ng/mL (ref. 130-097-744, Miltenyi).

Dissociation of Vasc-PDTs +/- PBMCs for flow cytometry. After chemotherapy treatments, Vasc-PDTs were priorly washed in PBS and pooled in a 1,5mL tube. PBS was removed and accutase was added. Up to ten resuspensions are done with low-binding tips, then, the tubes were incubated at 37°C with permanent agitation during five to ten minutes. Vasc-PDTs were dissociated into single cell culture and staining protocol for flow cytometry acquisition were performed.

IHC of patients' primary tissues and Vasc-PDTs. Vasc-PDTs were fixed in 4% PFA and embedded in Histogel specimen processing gel (ref. HG-4000-012, ThermoFisher Scientific) before dehydration in the Pearl. After paraffin inclusion, the blocs were sectioned on the Leica microtome at the size of 5µm. Then, immunohistochemistry (IHC) and standard hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) staining were performed on these sectioned slides. IHC staining was performed on the LEICA Bond-III system using the streptavidin-biotin-peroxidase complex method. The slides were prepared according to the following primary antibodies anti-TTF-1 (dilution 1:250 ref. ab76013, Abcam), anti-Ki-67 (dilution 1:5000; ref. LS-B13463-100, LS bio), anti-p40 (dilution 1:100; ref. RP163, Diagnostic Biosystems), anti-MUC1 (final concentration 0,25mg/mL; ref. NCL-MUC1-CORE, Novocastra), and anti-CK7 (dilution 1:300; ref. BSH-2018-100, Nordic BioSite). H&E staining were performed on paraffin sections that were prior deparaffinized in xylene and different solutions of ethanol. Coloration with hematoxylin and eosin solutions were done followed by dehydration with ethanol 100% and xylene.

Staining of the Vasc-PDTs embedded by fibrin gel. After 24h of fibrin gel embedding, the Vasc-PDTs embedded by fibrin gel were prior fixed with 4% PFA overnight at 4°C. 0,25% Triton X solution (ref. T-8787, Sigma) was added for 30 min at RT. 1% BSA blocking buffer (ref. A9647, Sigma) was then added for 4h at RT. Lectin staining (dilution 1:100, ref. UEA-1 lectin Vector Laboratories RL-1062) was performed for 24h. The stained Vasc-PDTs and gels were washed at least 4 times with PBS at 30min of interval (one washing was overnight at 4°C). Then anti-CD31 (dilution 1:250, ref. CB13678, Cell Applications) was prepared and let for 72h of incubation at 4°C. Secondary antibody directed against the primary antibody was incubated for 24h at 4°C (dilution 1:200, ref A32723, Invitrogen). Finally, DAPI solution (dilution 1:3000 in distilled water, ref. B-2883, Sigma) was added for one hour at RT. PBS washing was done before acquisition in LSM Zeiss 800 confocal microscopy.

Secretome analysis. Cytokines and interleukines analyzed were CD31 (PECAM-1), EGF, FGF-2, G-CSF, HGF, IL-8, Leptin, PDGF-BB, Syndecan, VEGF-A, VEGF-D, Angiopoietin-1, BMP-9, EMMPRIN, Follistatin, HB-EGF, LYVE-1 and TIE-2. These cytokines and interleukines were designed by Procarta Plex with the Human Angiogenesis panel 18-plex. For experiments relative to co-culture with PBMCs, cytokines and interleukines analyzed were CD27, CD28, CD137 (4-1BB), G1TR, HVEM, BTLA, CD80, CD152 (CTLA4), IDO, LAG-3, PD-1, PD-L1, PD-L2 and TIM-3. These cytokines and interleukines were designed by Procarta Plex with the Human Immuno-oncology panel I 14-plex. Protocol was done according to the manufacturer's indications.

For quantification of IFN-γ in the supernatant, the IFN-γ human ELISA kit (ref. KHC4021) was used according to the supplier protocol.

Flow cytometry acquisition for analyses of PBMCs' subpopulations in PBMCs and dissociated Vasc-PDTs. Following the thawing of PBMCs, PBMCs subpopulation were investigated with cell surface markers staining. The PBMCs subpopulations were studied with this panel: Live/dead FVS575V (dilution 1:1000; ref. L34955, Invitrogen), anti-CD45 V450 (ref. 560367, BD), anti-CD3 AF700 (ref. 317340, Biolegend), anti-CD14 V500 (ref. 561391, BD Biosciences), anti-CD16 FITC (ref. 335035, BD Biosciences), anti-HLA DR APC Cy7 (ref. 307618, Biolegend), anti-CD4 PE (ref. 555347, BD Pharmingen), anti-CD8 BV650 (ref. 301042, Biolegend), anti-CD20 PE Cy7 (ref. 130-111-340, Miltenyi), anti-CD56 PE Cy7 (ref. 130-113-313, Miltenyi), anti-CD11c PE Cy5 (ref. 301610, Biolegend) and anti-CD123 PerCP Cy5,5 (ref. 396714, Biolegend).

Incubation with Live/Dead reagent and antibodies was for 30minutes at 4°C in the darkness. After 30min of incubation, cells were centrifuged at 350g during 8min at 4°C and resuspended in 100µL of PBS before acquisition on the MACSQuant 16 (Miltenyi Germany).

Declarations

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Author contributions

This project was conducted by H.-L. and supervised by G.H., J.M.-B., N.B.-J. and E.-Q.. The biopsies were provided by surgeons A.O., P.-E.F. and patients' primary tissue paraffin sections by V.L. C.-P. included all patients and provided patients' clinical data. J.D analyzed the data from transcriptomic part. H.-L. wrote the paper. J.-M.B., E.Q., G.H., Y.I.-G. and N.B.-J participated to the manuscript. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

Data availability

The datasets used and/or analysed during the current study available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

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Table

Table 1. List of lung cancer patients' samples used for the generation of vascularized patient-derived tumoroids. Several readouts were studied including characterization (by IHC and 3' RNA sequencing) to verify the maintenance of tumoral genes associated to lung cancer, standard of care treatments (cisplatin + pemetrexed or bevacizumab treatments) to predict vascularized patient-derived tumoroids sensitivity to two different therapies and co-culture with autologous PBMCs for the interest on immune landscape in prediction of chemotherapy clinical responses.

Patient identity	Sourcing	Gender	Age	NSCLC subtype, TNM score and stage	Status PD-L1	Supplementary informations
21T 414	CRB Strasbourg	Male	77	Adenocarcinoma T1bN0M0 (Stage IA)	PD-L1 negative	KRAS mutation G12D Simple monitoring
21T 469	CRB Strasbourg	Male	69	Suspected adenocarcinoma Definitive diagnostic : large cell neuroendocrine carcinoma	Unknown	Adjuvant chemotherapy : cisplatin + navelbine but poor tolerance 6 months post-surgery : bone and cerebral metastasis => Radiotherapy indicated but refused by the patient
21T 554	CRB Strasbourg	Female	64	Adenocarcinoma T3N2M0 (Stage IIIB)	Unknown	Preoperative treatment: cisplatin-pemetrexed + pembrolizumab or placebo (clinical study MK3475-671) Follow-up : Cerebral and sacrum metastasis (radiotherapy)
21T 226	CRB Strasbourg	Female	60	Adenocarcinoma T2aN2M0 (Stage IIIA)	PD-L1 80%	Neoadjuvant chemotherapy before surgery Metastatic recurrence
22T 194	CRB Strasbourg	Female	54	Adenocarcinoma pT1cN0M0 (Stage IA3)	PD-L1 negative	Mutation L858R exon 21 EGFR No adjuvant treatment
22T 245	CRB Strasbourg	Male	54	Adenocarcinoma pT2aN2M0 (Stage IIIA)	PD-L1 negative	No mutations Theoretical indication for chemotherapy but refused by the patient
22T 351	CRB Strasbourg	Female	67	Adenocarcinoma (pT4)	Unknown	PDL1 positive Neo adjuvant Chemotherapy
21269-007	Fidelis Research	Male	77	Adenocarcinoma T1N0M1 (stage IV)	Unknown	Current smoker and drinker
21269-008	Fidelis Research	Female	68	Adenocarcinoma T2N2M0 (Stage IIIA)	Unknown	Life-long non-smoker and non-drinker
21269-013	Fidelis Research	Female	53	Adenocarcinoma T2N0M0 (Stage IIA)	Unknown	Life-long non drinker Current smoker
21269-020	Fidelis Research	Male	61	Adenocarcinoma T2N3M1	Unknown	Current smoker and drinker

Figures

Figure 1

Vascularized PDTs recapitulate the lung adenocarcinoma-associated markers of the primary tissue after 7 days of culture. H&E colorations and IHC-staining images of paraffin sections of lung cancer tissues and matched PDT. Lung adenocarcinoma markers such as TTF-1, CK7 and MUC1 were stained. P40 is a squamous cell carcinoma marker and was also used to confirm the lung adenocarcinoma subtype according to anatomopathologists' routine test. The IHC staining was performed on a subset of 4 different patients. Scale bar in IHC photos, 100µm

(A) Tumor versus Healthy primary cells Tumoroids versus Healthy organoids

(B)

21T 414		21T 469		21T 554		
Primary cells	vasc-PDT	Primary cells	vasc-PDT	Primary cells	vasc-PDT	
						CEACAM5
						CEACAM6
						EPCAM
						KRT17
						KRT6A
						KRT7
						KRT8
						KRT15
						KRT18
						KRT18P11
						KRT18P13
						KRTCAP3
						NAPSA
						MUC1
						MUC21
						MUC4
						MUC5AC
						MUC5B
						S100A7
						S100A9
						S100A8
						S100A14
						S100P
						SERPINA1
						SERPINE2
						SERPINEB1
						SLC34A2
						TTF1

Figure 2

Vascularized PDTs recapitulate the lung adenocarcinoma-associated markers of the primary tissue after 7 days of culture. (A) Volcano Plot showing the different upregulated genes in the tumoral primary cells versus healthy primary cells as well as in the vascularized PDTs versus the healthy organoids. **(B)** Table showing the main lung cancer-associated genes that are significantly upregulated in the tumoral primary cells versus healthy primary cells as well as in the vascularized tumoroids versus the healthy organoids according to the 3' RNA sequencing analysis

Figure 3

Generation of PDTs including a preliminar vascular network by incorporation of adipose tissue derived microvessels (A) In vitro angiogenesis assay. Created with BioRender. Characterization of capillary-like structures with CD31/PECAM-1 & UEA-lectin staining of PDTs presenting capillary-like structures. Scale bar: 100µm. **(B)** Cell viability assay of untreated (mock) and bevacizumab-treated of Vasc-PDTs (n=5) **(C)** IHC photos of capillary-like structures of untreated and bevacizumab-treated patient-derived tumoroids. Scale bar: 100µm **(D)** Graph demonstrated changes in secreted cytokines between untreated and PDTs treated with anti-VEGF (n=5). IL-8 and VEGF-A showed significant effect (increase and decrease respectively) (p< 0,05 determined by t-test Student).

Figure 4

Co-culture of autologous immune cells and vasc-PDTs for an immuno-oncology in vitro model (A) Assessment of immune cells infiltration toward Vasc-PDTs by IHC. Scale bar : 100 μ m. (n=6: 21269-007 in light pink, 21269-008 in yellow, 21269-013 in blue, 21269-020 in green, 22T 194 in pink and 22T 245 in black) **(B)** Assessment of immune cells infiltration toward PDTs by flow cytometry for CD45+ immune cells **(C)** Cell viability assessment after 96h of LPS and chemotherapy treatments in monoculture and co-culture with PBMCs (n=6) **(D)** % of CD4+, CD8+, CD20+ and CD56+ immune cells are checked within patient-derived tumoroids co-cultured with autologous PBMCs **(E)** Proteins implied in immunosuppression are assessed in Vasc-PDTs lysates with immuno-oncology panel 1 from Procarta Plex technology in the 3 patients where level of proteins were detectable 21269-008, 22T 194 and 22T 245 (n=3). Statistics analyses were performed using ANOVA test, data were presented as mean \pm SD.

Supplementary Files

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